

Kinetics and Mechanism of Metal Ion Catalysed Aquation of *Cis*-Oxalatoamminebis (ethylenediamine) Cobalt(III) Complex

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The aquation of *cis*-oxalatoamminebis(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) complex has been studied in the presence of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Al(III), Ga(III), In(III), and Fe(III) ions. The oxalate bridged binuclear complexes, $(en)_2(NH_3)CoC_2O_4M^{(n+1)+}$, act as the catalytically active labile intermediates in the hydrolysis reaction, the stability constants of which have been measured. The catalytic activities of the metal ions vary in the order: Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II) and In(III) < Al(III) ~ Ga(III) < Fe(III). The sequence $k_{(M^{2+})} < k_{(M^{3+})}$ is also observed. It is presumed that the metal ion catalyzed aquation occurs with Co-O bond fission.

THE aquation reaction of salicylato¹, oxalato², and malonato³ pentaammine Cobalt(III) complexes are catalysed by metal ions. It has been shown that the binuclear complexes of the metal ions with these cobalt(III) substrates are involved as the reactive intermediates in such reactions. In continuation of our earlier work⁴ we report in this paper the study of the kinetics and mechanism of acid hydrolysis of *cis* $(en)_2(NH_3)Co.C_2O_4H^{2+}$ in the presence of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Al(III), Ga(III), In(III), and Fe(III).

Experimental

The *cis* $[(en)_2(NH_3)CoC_2O_4H](ClO_4)_2$ was obtained from our earlier work⁴. Stock solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared and estimated for the metal ion and free acid contents in the usual way^{1,2}. Baker analysed reagent perchloric acid and Riedel sample of sodium perchlorate were used to adjust acidity and ionic strength of the reaction medium. B.D.H.(A.R.) sodium oxalate was dried at 105° for 4 hr before it was used for standardising permanganate. Dowex50W-X8 resin in acid form was used for ion exchange experiments.

Kinetics: Requisite amounts of perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate, and metal perchlorate solutions were equilibrated in 50 ml flasks in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature. After sufficient time was allowed for thermal equilibrium a known weight of the complex was transferred into the flask. The complex dissolved quickly on shaking and the volume was made up with distilled water previously equilibrated at the same temperature. The rate of aquation of the oxalato complex was followed by estimating the oxalate content of aliquot (5 ml) of the reaction mixture at convenient time intervals after it was subjected to cation exchange with H⁺ form of Dowex 50W-X8 resin². N/100 KMnO₄ was used as the titrant.

The pseudo-first-order rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained from the slopes of the least squares best line plots of $\ln(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. time (in seconds), where V_t and V_∞ stand for the permanganate titre values at time t and for complete reaction respectively. V_∞ for all runs were calculated from the weight of the complex and then corrected for the titration blank. The rate constants (k_{obs}) given in Table 1 were calculated from 40-60% of the oxalate release.

Results

The observed rate constants (k_{obs}) collected in Table 1 clearly indicate that the metal ions under investigation catalyse the aquation of the oxalato complex. Mn(II) and Fe(III) appear to be the least and the most effective catalyst respectively. Furthermore it is noted that at constant hydrogen ion concentration, $(k_{obs} - k_{obs}')/[M^{n+}]$ ($k_{obs}' = k_{obs}$ at $[M^{n+}] = 0$) decreases with increasing concentration of the metal ions. This observation is consistent with the equilibrium preassociation of the Co(III) substrate with the catalyst metal ions followed by the aquation of the resulting binuclear species, $(en)_2(NH_3)CoC_2O_4M^{(n+1)+}$, at rates characteristic of the associated metal ions. The pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , for the aquation of the complex at constant metal ion and hydrogen ion concentrations is given by

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_0 K_1/[H^+] + k_1 + k_2[H^+] + k_3 K_1 K_2[M^{n+}]/[H^+]}{1 + K_1/[H^+] + K_1 K_2[M^{n+}]/[H^+]}$$

... (1)

The rate constants, k_0 , k_1 , k_2 , k_3 and the equilibrium constants K_1 , K_2 are defined as follows:

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Eq. (1) can easily be transformed to the form

$$1/(k_{obs} - k'_{obs}) = a + ab/[M^{n+}] \quad \dots (2)$$

where k'_{obs} is as defined earlier, $a = 1/(k_3 - k'_{obs})$ and $b = ([H^+] + K_1)/K_1K_2$. The two parameters (a, b) of eq. (2) were evaluated by fitting the rate data to eq. (2) by means of a computer programme which varied a , and b and minimized $\sum[(Y_{cal} - Y_{exp})/\sigma(Y_{exp})]^2$ where Y_{exp} and Y_{cal} stand for the experimental and calculated values of $1/(k_{obs} - k'_{obs})$ respectively. $\sigma(Y_{exp})$ is the error of Y_{exp} computed from the errors of k_{obs} and k'_{obs} . The values of k'_{obs} used in this calculation were taken from our earlier work⁴ either as such (at 55° and 65°) or by extrapolating $\log k'_{obs}$ vs. $1/T$ plot to the experimental temperatures (i.e. 35° and 45°). The stability constants (K_2) of the binuclear complexes are based on $K_1 = 0.0078$ (35°), 0.011 (45°), 0.0151 (55°) and 0.0209M (65°) which were chosen from the $\log K_1$ vs. $1/T$ plot. The values of K_1 at 25, 55, 60, 65, and 70° and 1.0M ionic strength have been reported⁴ to be 0.0057 (± 0.0005), 0.011 (± 0.002), 0.017 (± 0.003), 0.020 (± 0.005), and 0.030 (± 0.005)M respectively.

TABLE I—RATE DATA FOR METAL ION CATALYSED EQUATION OF (en)₂(NH₃)CoC₂O₄H²⁺.

Ionic strength = 1.0M						
10 ² [M ⁿ⁺], (M)	10 ² [H ⁺], (M)	10 ³ [Complex], (M)	10 ⁶ k _{obs} *, sec ⁻¹	10 ⁶ k ₃ , sec ⁻¹	K ₂ , M ⁻¹	
1	2	3	4	5	6	
M = Mn(II)						
55.0°(±0.1)°						
0.00	2.0	1.98	1.9 (±0.2)			
5.16	2.0	2.14	3.99(±0.15)			
10.2	2.0	2.02	4.38(±0.35)			
15.4	2.0	2.15	4.52(±0.24)	4.92(±0.29)	102(±34)	
65.0(±0.1)°						
0.00	2.0	1.89	4.29(±0.18)			
5.16	2.0	1.55	9.92(±0.37)			
10.2	2.0	1.74	11.2 (±0.2)			
15.4	2.0	1.98	13.1 (±0.5)	16.0(±0.4)	33.2(±2.8)	
M = Co(II)						
55.0°(±0.1)°						
3.0	2.0	1.70	6.25(±0.19)			
6.0	2.0	1.71	7.40(±0.08)			
9.0	2.0	1.68	7.90(±0.27)	9.33(±0.29)	110(±11)	
65.0°(±0.1)°						
3.0	2.0	1.50	13.7 (±0.5)			
6.0	2.0	1.41	17.3(±0.4)			
9.0	2.0	1.68	19.3 (±0.5)	24.3(±0.5)	61.2(±3.9)	
M = Ni(II)						
55.0°(±0.1)°						
2.1	2.0	1.35	6.80(±0.60)			
4.2	2.0	1.43	7.90(±0.60)			
6.3	2.0	1.42	8.41(±0.51)	9.66(±0.49)	189(±46)	
65.0°(±0.1)°						
2.1	2.0	1.51	15.2 (±0.7)			
4.2	2.0	1.41	18.5 (±0.7)			
6.3	2.0	1.42	21.8 (±0.5)	29.5(±0.6)	67.8(±4.3)	
M = Cu(II)						
55.0°(±0.1)°						
0.00	10.0	1.74	3.40(±0.18)			
1.0	10.0	1.42	21.8 (±0.4)			
2.0	10.0	1.53	28.6 (±1.2)			
4.0	10.0	1.31	34.0 (±1.3)	42.8(±0.7)	668(±26)	

TABLE 1—Contd.

$10^2[M^{n+}]$, (M)	$10^2[H^+]$, (M)	$10^3[\text{Complex}]$, (M)	$10^3k_{obs}^*$, sec ⁻¹	10^3k_3 , sec ⁻¹	K_2 , M ⁻¹
1	2	3	4	5	6
			65.0°(±0.1)°		
0.00	10.0	1.55	6.68(±0.27)		
1.0	10.0	1.74	37.9 (±1.0)		
2.0	10.0	1.43	51.8 (±2.5)		
4.0	10.0	1.36	70.0 (±2.5)	111(±2)	238(±9)
			M = Zn(II)		
			55.0°(±0.1)°		
3.0	2.0	1.86	4.85(±0.22)		
6.0	2.0	1.80	5.77(±0.28)		
9.0	2.0	1.75	6.50(±0.23)	8.25(±0.36)	65.5(±8.1)
			65.0°(±0.1)°		
3.0	2.0	1.42	11.6 (±0.5)		
6.0	2.0	1.35	14.7 (±0.5)		
9.0	2.0	1.73	16.3 (±0.5)	21.0(±0.5)	54.3(±4.5)
			M = Fe(III)		
			35.0°(±0.1)°		
0.00	10.0	—	0.63		
0.440	10.0	1.86	9.78(±0.30)		
0.882	10.0	1.56	14.5 (±0.5)		
1.320	10.0	1.60	16.1 (±0.3)	23.3(±0.3)	2289(±92)
			45.0°(±0.1)°		
0.00	10.0	—	1.38		
0.20	10.0	1.59	25.6 (±1.6)		
0.40	10.0	1.43	39.7 (±3.8)		
0.60	10.0	1.62	51.0 (±3.8)	104(±5)	1544(±104)
			M = Al(III)		
			45.0°(±0.1)°		
0.00	5.0	—	0.80		
0.61	5.0	1.50	13.5 (±0.4)		
1.21	5.0	1.68	20.2 (±0.4)		
1.82	5.0	1.59	27.0 (±0.6)	52.9(±0.6)	289(±5)
			55.0°(±0.1)°		
0.61	10.0	1.73	23.0 (±1.0)		
1.21	10.0	1.35	35.0 (±1.0)		
1.82	10.0	1.39	53.7 (±2.5)	212(±5)	121(±3)
			M = Ga(III)		
			35.0°(±0.1)°		
0.242	10.0	1.35	7.41(±0.34)		
0.485	10.0	1.40	12.5 (±0.6)		
0.727	10.0	1.45	16.8 (±1.0)	54.6(±1.7)	813(±32)
			55.0°(±0.1)°		
0.00	20.0	—	4.22		
0.242	20.0	1.31	24.8 (±1.1)		
0.484	20.0	1.60	42.2 (±3.2)		
1.210	20.0	1.81	77.7 (±3.3)	216(±7)	630(±26)
			M = In(III)		
			45.0°(±0.1)°		
0.50	5.0	1.52	5.32(±0.27)		
1.00	5.0	1.56	6.67(±0.24)		
2.00	5.0	1.58	8.50(±0.20)	11.0(±0.2)	829(±49)
			55.0°(0.1)°		
0.00	5.0	1.75	2.45(±0.15)		
0.50	5.0	1.53	16.0 (±1.0)		
1.00	5.0	1.27	21.7 (±1.0)		
1.35	5.0	1.44	23.7 (±1.0)	34.2(±1.0)	651(±51)

* The errors quoted for k_{obs} were calculated from the least squares standard deviations of the slopes of the pseudo-first-order kinetic plots.

Discussion

The results of the present investigation also indicate (cf. also ref. 2) that M^{n+} and $(en)_2(NH_3)CoC_2O_4^+$ ions interact in aqueous medium to form the binuclear species, $(en)_2(NH_3)CoC_2O_4M^{(n+1)+}$. The stabilities of the binuclear complexes of the bivalent metal ions follow the Irving-Williams sequence: $Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II)$. The order of stability of the binuclear complexes of the trivalent metal ions is $Al(III) < In(III) \sim Ga(III) < Fe(III)$.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR k_3 PATH

Metal ion	ΔH^* kcal/mole	ΔS^* , e.u.
Mn(II)	25.3	- 5.8
Co(II)	20.4	-19.4
Ni(II)	23.9	- 8.7
Cu(II)	20.3	-16.7
Zn(II)	20.0	-21.0
Al(III)	28.1	+10.0
Ga(III)	20.6	-13.0
In(III)	23.0	- 9.0
Fe(III)	28.5	+13.0

The rate constants (k_3) associated with the metal ion catalysed path follow the sequence: $Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II)$ and $In(III)$

$< Al(III) \sim Ga(III) < Fe(III)$. It is apparent that the stabilities of the binuclear complexes parallel their reactivities. Furthermore the sequence $k_{3(M^{2+})} < k_{3(M^{3+})}$, indicates that the rate increases with the increase of the positive charge and hence with the decrease of basicity of the leaving groups. The rate vs. pK of the leaving group correlation fits with the Co-O fission mechanism for the k_3 path^{1,2}. For all the metal ions under investigation, k_3 of the oxalato-pentaammine Cobalt(III) and *cis* oxalato ammine bis(ethylene diamine) Cobalt(III) substrates are related to each other as: $\log k_{3(NH_3)} = -6.2 + 1.2 \log k_{3(en)}$ (at 55°). This straight line relationship suggests that the effect of changing the ligand environment of Cobalt(III) does not bring about any significant change in the mechanism of aquation of the binuclear complexes.

The activation parameters for the k_3 path are given in Table 2. These data for Cu(II), Al(III), In(III), and Fe(III) compare well with the corresponding data for the oxalato-pentaammine Cobalt(III) complex². This observation provides further support in favour of a common mechanism (i.e., rate limiting Co-O fission) in the metal ion catalysed path of aquation of both the Cobalt(III) substrates.

References

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